

Biochemical Characterization and Screening of the Halotolerant Marine Bacteria for Potential Alleviation of Saline Stress

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ABSTRACT

Soil salinization is an escalating global issue that affects approximately 20% of cultivated land and severely limits the productivity of most non-halophytic crops. Unlike halophytes, agricultural crops lack specialized mechanisms to survive salinity stress. This study aimed to evaluate the potential of marine bacteria to mitigate salt stress and facilitate germination in non-halophytic crops at elevated salt concentrations.

Five strains of Marine Bacteria (MB-1 to MB-5) were isolated from a coastal seawater sample. These isolates underwent a Saline Tolerance Test at 1%, 3%, and 5% NaCl Concentrations. These isolates were characterised using standard biochemical tests, including Gram staining, catalase activity, hydrogen sulphide test, Methyl Red and Voges's Proskauer tests

Experimental tests performed projected results that were similar for each strain of the isolated marine bacteria. In particular, the carbohydrate utilization profile was analyzed using the Methyl Red and Voges-Proskauer tests. Tests like catalase, determined that the strain possess the capability of suppressing the levels of Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS) where researchers convey that this product is produced in higher levels under stress. The tests performed on these bacterial strains resulted in various inferences for all the strains, which projected a healthier outcome for superior applications in the ability of plants to sustain salinity conditions.

INTRODUCTION

Salinity stress inhibits plant growth and development, seed germination, and yield (1). The primary cause of salinity stress is technically due to the intrusion of the salt water into the freshwater, rising temperatures, and increased sea levels. The excessive use of the fertilizers, poor management and deep agricultural practices on the cultivated lands were the dominant sources of the secondary cause of higher salinity issues (2).

The bacteria that survive in the sea are of two types: halophilic and halotolerant. Halophilic organisms usually thrive at higher salt concentrations whereas halotolerant organisms were tolerant to higher salt concentrations and can survive even without any salt concentration (3). Halophilic bacteria were micro-organisms which can withstand high salt concentrations in saline environments.

They consist of and survive through unique metabolic pathways and enzymes. This allows them to maintain cellular integrity (4). Halophilic microorganisms are said to be obligate salt-lovers, with a minimum salt concentration of 0.2M.

Halotolerant bacteria do not have specific salt concentration requirements and were able to be tolerant to high salt concentrations. The specific bacterial strains isolated in this study were labelled as Marine Bacteria (MB). The ability of these bacteria to tolerate high salt concentration is adopted as an application for analysing the salinization of soil and water. These bacteria can sustain and survive at high pH, temperature, and salinity conditions, which is considered beneficial in the industrial sector (4).

Halophytes maintain cellular homeostasis by accumulating compatible solutes in the plant cells and restricting excess salt in their vacuoles. They were also said to prevent the accumulation of sodium ions inside the cells. Vacuoles have a specially modified lipid layer composition that blocks the leakage of sodium ions. In Glycophytes, limited sodium ions are said to be absorbed, or older tissues function as storage compartments. The chief issue lies in the saline condition, if high, the plants lose the ability to survive completely and are unable to manage ionic stress. Both halophytes and glycophytes cannot survive under extremely high salt conditions, and this depends on the pathways that occur in the distinct strains and species of plants, which makes it possible to sustain or does not survive in high salt conditions (5).

Salt tolerance activity is said to be dependent on the functioning of the plasma membrane (6). Across the plasma membrane there was conveyed to have a sodium proton antiporter which were said to be crucial transmembrane, must be provided with sensors to detect and maintain the pH and Na^+ ion concentration (6). The calcium signals present in the cytosol act as machines to export the sodium ions out of the cell. The SOS3 sensors release kinase complexes that further activate the phosphorylated target proteins, such as SOS1. This SOS1 encodes a higher sodium proton antiporter to exclude cells from plant cells. Cytosolic enzymes were said to be not tolerant to sodium inhibition in few halophytes. Supposedly, the large amounts of sodium were actively accumulated in the vacuole compartments, maintaining high levels of sodium (6).

Unlike halophytes, glycophytes can not resist higher salt concentrations and typically do not survive. These plants exclude sodium and maintain low levels of sodium inside the cells due to the lower expression of the sodium proton antiporters, which was conveyed under lower salinity conditions. The accumulation of sodium in the shoot region decreases stomatal function and osmotic potential. This inhibits plant growth and promotes cell senescence and death. As the accumulation of sodium is hazardous to plants, they exert all their efforts to take up potassium ions into the cells (7).

Materials & Methods

Gram staining [8,9]

Reagents:

- Crystal violet for staining gram-positive bacteria.
- Gram's iodine used as a mordant.
- 70% alcohol for destaining and
- Safranin to stain the gram-negative bacteria (8).

Procedure:

- A drop of freshly cultured marine bacterial strains (MB-1 to MB-5) was added onto a clean slide.
- The cells were stained with crystal violet, retained for 60 seconds and washed.
- Iodine was added, incubated for 60 seconds and washed.
- Alcohol was added, retained strictly for 5-10 seconds and washed.
- Safranin was added, retained for 45 seconds and washed.
- The slides were observed under the light microscope.

Salinity tolerance Test [9,10]

Reagents:

- Zobell marine media with agar and NaCl concentrations (1%, 3%, and 5%) (9).

Procedure:

- Add sterile media to sterile petri plates and allow it solidify.
- Using a sterile inoculation loop, single streak the bacterial strains (MB-1 to MB-5) on the solid media plate.
- Incubate at 37°C for 24hrs (10).

Catalase test [11]

Reagent: Hydrogen peroxide

Procedure:

- A drop of fresh bacterial culture (MB-1 to MB-5) was added to each slide.
- Add one or two drops of hydrogen peroxide.
- Observe the results (11).

Hydrogen Sulfide Test (H_2S)

Reagents:

- Beef extract
- Peptone
- Sodium thiosulphate
- Ferrous ammonium sulphate
- Agar

Procedure:

- Add 3ml of the prepared media to the gas detector tubes.
- Bacterial strains (MB-1 to MB-5) of 200ml were added to each tube.
- The tubes were incubated at 37°C for 5 days.

Methyl Red and Voges Proskauer Test (MR-VP) [12, 13]

Reagents:

- Buffered peptone
- Glucose
- Dipotassium phosphate
- Methyl Red indicator

Procedure:

- To one set of five test tubes, add 5ml of media was added to each.
- Add 100µl of bacterial strains (MB-1 to MB-5) were added to the test tubes and incubated at 37°C for 24 hrs.
- A few drops of methyl red indicator were added to each test tube (12).
- The same procedure was followed for another set of five test tubes until incubation.
- A few drops of Barritt's Reagent A, which is alpha-naphthol solution, and Barritt's Reagent B, potassium hydroxide solution, were added to each test tube (13).

Results

Gram staining

After gram staining, the slides were focused under a light microscope at 40x lens. All bacterial strains (MB-1, MB-2, MB-3, MB-4, and MB-5) were noticed to be in rod shaped and pink colour bacteria as shown in the Fig 1.

Fig 1 -Result of Gram Staining

Salt tolerance test

All strains showed growth in 1% NaCl, as shown in Fig 2(a). In 3% NaCl, MB-1 to MB-4 showed positive results, whereas MB-5 showed mild growth, as shown in Fig 2(b). Except for the MB-4 strain, the other strains exhibited growth, which was recorded as a positive result, as shown in Fig 2(c). The intensity the growth was observed, as mentioned in the Table 1.

Fig 2(a) - Growth in 1% NaCl

Fig 2(b) - Growth in 3% NaCl

FIG 2(c) - Growth in 5% NaCl

Table 1 -Result of Salt Tolerance Test

MB Strain	1% NaCl Concentration	3% NaCl Concentration	5% NaCl Concentration
MB-1	Acceptable growth	Acceptable growth	Mild growth
MB-2	Acceptable growth	Acceptable growth	Acceptable growth
MB-3	Acceptable growth	Acceptable growth	Acceptable growth
MB-4	Acceptable growth	Acceptable growth	No growth
MB-5	Moderate growth	Moderate growth	Mild growth

Catalase Test

The vigorous effervescence (bubble formation) occurred for a longer time, which is a positive result of catalase reaction that occurred in the MB-2 and MB-3 strains as shown in Fig 3. The MB-1 and MB-4 strains showed mild positive results. The MB-5 strains showed negative result.

Fig 3 -Results of Catalase Test

Hydrogen Sulphide Test

MB-2 and MB-3 exhibited strong positive reactions, characterized by extensive blackening of the medium. The MB-1 and MB-5 strains showed mild positive results, whereas the MB-4 strain was observed to be negative as shown in Fig 4.

Fig 4 -Result of H₂S test

Methyl Red and Voges Proskauer Test

After an incubation period in MR-VP broth, the addition of the Methyl Red indicator resulted in a distinct yellow colour across all five tubes, which was a negative result. All marine bacterial strain isolates showed negative results, as shown in Fig 5(a).

In the Voges Proskauer test, it is observed and recognized that all the five strains project a negative result equally with black-green precipitate formation as shown in Fig 5(b).

FIG 5(a) - Result of MR test

FIG 5(b) -Result of VP test

The results of biochemical tests performed are arranged in the below Table 2.

Table 2 -Results of Biochemical Tests performed

MB Strain	Type of cell	Shape of cell	Catalase Test	H ₂ S Test	Methyl Red Test	Voges Proskauer Test
MB-1	Gram -ve	Rod shape	Mild +ve	Highly +ve	-ve	-ve
MB-2	Gram -ve	Rod shape	Highly +ve	Highly +ve	-ve	-ve
MB-3	Gram -ve	Rod shape	Highly +ve	Highly +ve	-ve	-ve
MB-4	Gram -ve	Rod shape	Mild +ve	-ve	-ve	-ve
MB-5	Gram -ve	Rod shape	-ve	Mild +ve	-ve	-ve

DISCUSSION

The isolation of halotolerant bacilli from coastal seawater provides vital biological resources for addressing the global challenge of agricultural soil salinization. The focus was on marine bacteria to identify their capability of facilitating crop survival in highly saline agricultural lands. This research aimed to bridge the gap between the plant growth promotion and the resilience of marine bacteria under osmotic stress.

In the salt tolerance test, there was no growth in the MB-4 strain, and a gradual decline of growth was observed in MB-1 and MB-5 strains in 5% NaCl indicating that this strain cannot survive in a 5% salt concentration. The strains that were positive and could maintain and survive ion homeostasis and structural adaptations(14) in all three salt concentrations were MB-2 and MB-3. In the gram staining test, it was identified that these bacterial strains were gram negative bacilli. In the catalase test, a the positive result implies the release of catalase enzymes, to breakdown hydrogen peroxide to hydrogen and oxygen, suggesting a high capacity for neutralizing oxidative stress and a decline in the production of reactive oxygen species(2). The negative results showed the absence of catalase reaction, where hydrogen peroxide breakdown did not occur. The positive results of the H₂S test indicated the ability to utilize sulphur as a terminal electron acceptor in saline environments, especially in MB-2 and MB-3. In the MR test, the yellow colour indicates a final pH of 6.2 or higher within the medium (15). This indicates that these strains do not produce sufficiently stable acid end-products, such as lactic, acetic, or formic acid, to significantly lower the pH. In VP test it can be reported as these marine bacterial strains cannot produce the neutral end products such as acetoin especially by the butylene glycol pathway as they are notices to show negative results(13).

The results were as expected, and no difficulty was encountered in the procedures, and interpretation, as the tests conducted were well known and basic tests for identifying the abilities of the bacteria. Based on these results, further research techniques can be initiated using these common tests. In any research, these common tests play a crucial in understanding the basic characteristics and features of the bacteria, and additional tests can be performed.

Previous studies, particularly those focusing on coastal regions in India, Egypt, and Tunisia, have highlighted the isolation, characterization, and application of diverse strains, most notably from the *Bacillus*, *Halomonas*, *Staphylococcus*, and *Pseudomonas* genera(7). Research indicates that marine-derived and coastal halotolerant bacteria offer superior mitigation of salt stress in *Solanum lycopersicum* (tomato) compared to inland strains because of their evolved extreme resilience (up to 15-20% NaCl). *Halomonas* sp. (SVHM8 and SVCN6) and *Bacillus* sp. (SVHM1.1) isolated from halophytic plant rhizospheres (e.g., *Sesuvium verrucosum*) have identified several high performing microbial strains capable of enhancing growth and including salt tolerance at the intersection of halotolerant bacteria, bio-priming, and peanut (*Arachis hypogaea*) cultivation. *Klebsiella* sp. (specifically strain MBE02), *Pseudomonas* sp., and *Bacillus*

sp. (including *B. velezensis* and *B. subtilis*) have demonstrated significant growth promotion in peanuts (9).

Further research and analysis of these bioinoculant preparations can be done by performed by conducting other biochemical and solubilization tests to determine the ability of the bacteria to support plant survival. The genetic material of the bacteria can also be isolated to proceed with the experiments, where the production of bacterial enzymes deteriorates the levels of different stresses plants.

CONCLUSION

The marine bacterial strains exhibited promising metabolic activity, with strains MB-2 and MB-3 showing particularly strong positive results for salt tolerance, catalase activity, and H₂S production. Both strains were identified as rod-shaped gram-negative bacteria. Their ability to form healthy colonies under saline conditions indicates strong adaptability to varying salinity levels while maintaining their metabolic functions. Biochemical tests further confirmed their efficiency, including hydrogen sulphide production and high catalase activity, which enables the breakdown of hydrogen peroxide. Both strains tested negative in the MR-VP assay. In contrast, the remaining strains showed weaker metabolic performance, higher acidification, and reduced tolerance to salinity stress.

Owing to their efficiency, MB-2 and MB-3 show a strong potential for use as bio-priming agents or soil inoculants in agriculture. These strains can enhance plant root and shoot growth by alleviating osmotic stress through plant-microbe interactions and symbiosis. Overall, the findings suggest that these bacterial strains may support crop productivity under saline conditions, although further research is needed to address global salinity stress in agriculture.

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